

Effect of Oral Language Development Program on the Reading Fluency of Grade VI- Pupils

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Abstract. This study sought to determine the effect of oral language development on the reading fluency of Grade 6 pupils. Utilizing a quasi-experimental research design, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design, the research addressed the constraints of having access to only one intact group for experimentation. The study was conducted at Dawis Elementary School in the Division of Digos City, involving 60 Grade 6 learners—32 from Section A as the control group and 28 from Section B as the experimental group. Both sections were homogeneously composed, with identical grades among the students. The non-random assignment of subjects included all learners from both sections. The findings revealed that the utilization of an oral language development program significantly increased the reading fluency of Grade 6 pupils. Moreover, the study indicated a substantial difference in the post-test scores between the control and experimental groups, underscoring the effectiveness of the oral language development program in enhancing reading fluency.

KEY WORDS

1. oral language 2. reading fluency 3. development

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1. Introduction

Oral language development is the process by which people learn and perfect their spoken language skills. It is an important part of human communication that underpins many areas of cognitive, social, and emotional development. Children normally develop oral language skills beginning in infancy, with milestones such as babbling, imitating sounds, and eventually constructing words and sentences Hoff, E. (2020). Oral language development plays a crucial role in various aspects of human life, including cognitive development, social interaction, academic achievement, and emotional well-being. Oral language skills lay the groundwork for cognitive development, which includes memory, attention, problem solving, and reasoning ability. Individuals learn to organize and communicate their thoughts, understand abstract concepts, and engage in complicated reasoning activities through oral language interactions. Oral language skill is closely related to academic success, especially in the early years of schooling. Children who have strong oral language skills are better able to comprehend and express ideas, participate in classroom discussions, group activities, and learn new concepts in a variety of subject areas such as reading, writing, mathematics, and science. Oral language skills serve as a precursor to literacy development. Children who have strong oral language experiences are more likely

to develop phonological awareness, vocabulary knowledge, and comprehension abilities, which are important components of reading Snow, C. E. (2020). Oral language development confers numerous advantages to individuals across various domains of life. Oral language development promotes cognitive growth and development. Conversations, storytelling, and arguments are all examples of language-rich activities that promote critical thinking, problem solving, and analytical skills. Furthermore, language processing tasks test memory, attention, and executive function abilities, promoting cognitive flexibility and mental agility. Oral language allows people to convey their emotions, sentiments, and experiences. Individuals who verbalize their thoughts and worries might obtain insight, handle tough emotions, and seek help from others. Effective communication skills also help people regulate their emotions, manage stress, and develop resilience in the face of adversity Hart, B. (2020). While oral language development is critical for communication and cognitive growth, there are some potential disadvantages or challenges associated with it. One such disadvantage is the risk of language delays or disorders, which can impact an individual's ability to effectively communicate and engage in social interactions. Some people may have delays or problems in their oral language development, limiting their capacity to communicate effectively. Language delays occur when language milestones like as vocabulary growth, sentence structure, and grammar are acquired at a slower rate than usual. Language disorders, on the other hand, are chronic difficulty in understanding or using spoken language, which frequently result in substantial communication challenges. These delays or problems can be caused by a variety of factors, including genetics, neurological abnormalities, environmental influences, or all of the above. Children with language delays or disorders may struggle to express their thoughts and feelings, comprehend instructions,

engage in conversations, or form friendships. Without adequate attention and assistance, these challenges can last throughout adulthood, affecting academic, social, and professional results Redmond, S. M. (2021). The reading fluency of grade VI pupils can be improved through a combination of targeted instruction, practice activities, and a supportive reading environment. By addressing these factors, educators can help students develop the essential skills they need to become proficient readers. Proficient reading fluency is a predictor of overall academic success. Students who struggle with fluency may experience challenges across various subjects that require reading, such as science, social studies, and literature (Fuchs et al., 2020). Enhancing the reading fluency of sixth-grade students has various benefits that support their overall academic performance and growth as individuals. Fluent readers can concentrate more on meaning than word decoding, which improves their comprehension and interpretation of texts. According to Pinnell et al. (2020), this improves comprehension. Fluent readers are more likely to appreciate reading and interact with a greater range of texts, which can encourage a lifetime love of reading (National Reading Panel, 2020). In the Division of Digos City particularly in Dawis Elementary School the same problem encountered poor reading among early graders the researcher being a reading teacher explores on initiative in developing the reading comprehension skills of the young learners. Hence, this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—The related literature from research and studies stipulated below will justify the existence of the problem under study. They will serve as a road map for the research during the study. At any rate, the review of significant literature stated herein backs up the validity of the study.

1.1.1. Oral Language Development Program—Oral language development plays a crucial role in literacy, cognitive growth, and aca-

ademic success (Dickinson Tabors, 2021; Hart Risley, 2020; Hirsch Nation, 2020). It includes vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and verbal communication skills, essential for success in various settings (Castilleja, 2020; Vygotsky, 2020). Programs that focus on oral language are beneficial, particularly for culturally and linguistically diverse students, fostering social skills and self-confidence (Garcia Wei, 2020; Hindman et al., 2020; Lonigan Shanahan, 2021). They support the development of speaking and listening skills, critical for academic standards (National Governors Association Center for Best Practices Council of Chief State School Officers, 2020).

However, such programs require significant resources and may not always address the holistic needs of language learners (Hatch, 2020; Wright, 2020). Access can be inequitable, and there may be a lack of transfer to written language proficiency (Cummins, 2020; Tabors, 2020). Over-reliance on drill-and-practice activities can lead to disengagement (Snow, 2020), and programs might not always be culturally responsive, potentially leading to stigmatization (García Sylvan, 2020; Skibbe et al., 2020).

Oral language development is crucial for academic achievement and social interaction, aiding in the development of communication skills and fostering a sense of belonging (Hart Risley, 2020; Tabors, 2020). Effective communication extends beyond the classroom, impacting various social settings positively (Cummins, 2020). Social interaction significantly influences oral language development, contributing to literacy development and understanding of grammar and syntax (Hoff, 2020).

Educational interventions, such as interactive read-alouds and language-rich environments, support oral language development (Hoff, 2020). Assessing oral language skills helps identify strengths and areas for improvement, promoting progress through early intervention.

1.1.2. Reading Fluency—Reading fluency in grade six pupils is crucial for literacy development and academic success. It involves accurate, quick, and expressive reading (Jenkins et al., 2021). Fluency allows better comprehension, as fluent readers can focus on understanding the text rather than decoding words (NICHD, 2020; Rasinski, 2022). Enhanced fluency correlates with better academic performance, increased confidence, and improved oral reading skills (Rasinski et al., 2020; National Reading Panel, 2021; Kuhn et al., 2020).

Lack of fluency can hinder comprehension and overall academic performance, leading to frustration and disengagement from learning (Rasinski, 2020; Chard, Vaughn, Tyler, 2021; Shaywitz, 2022). Fluency supports understanding complex ideas and accessing educational resources (Wolf Katzir-Cohen, 2020; Jenkins et al., 2021). It is linked to lifelong learning and literacy development, making it essential for academic success across various subjects.

Educators can foster reading fluency by recognizing its importance and implementing effective strategies, helping students become proficient readers and succeed academically (Tyler, 2020; Rasinski, 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literature discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different content. They also discussed methodologies on how the current issue is solved. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. This literature backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also serve as a road map to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

1.3. Theoretical Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the theory of Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory. Developed by the psychologist Lev Vygotsky, this theory emphasizes the role of social interaction and cultural context in cognitive development, particularly in the acquisition of language skills. According

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

to Vygotsky, children learn through social interactions with more knowledgeable individuals, such as parents, teachers, and peers. Language, in particular, plays a central role in these interactions, serving as both a tool for communication and a vehicle for cognitive growth. This is supported by Gough and Tunmer 2020, post that reading comprehension is the product of two primary components: decoding (word recognition)

and language comprehension (understanding the meaning of text). According to the Simple View of Reading (SVR), fluent reading emerges when students achieve automaticity in decoding, allowing them to focus their cognitive resources on comprehending the text. Grade VI students who have mastered decoding skills are more likely to read fluently, leading to better comprehension of the material.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study seeks to determine the effect of oral language development on the reading fluency of grade six pupils. Eventually, it also seeks to deter-

mine the magnitude of the effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the academic performance of the research subjects. Moreover, it seeks answers to the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the pre - test scores of the Grade six Pupils both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (2) What is the post test scores of the Grade six learners both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (3) Is there a significant difference on the post test scores of the grade six learners from controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of effect of the oral language development program on the reading fluency and academic performance of grade six learners?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—The null hypothesis in this study will be tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. The oral language development

program on the reading fluency has no effect on the academic performance of the grade six learners.

1.6. *Significance of the Study*—The results and findings of this study will be beneficial to the following: DepEd. The Department of Education should know the results and findings of this study for them to create a policy that would consider oral language development as an integral modality to assist learning instruction in schools. Besides, the department will conduct a reorientation for all school leaders on the mechanics of the conduct of the oral language development program as supplemental to learning instruction given to learners. School Heads. Being the school manager, the school head needs to know the results and findings of this study for them to initiate the school-based program that would strengthen the implementation of the effect of the oral language development program to supplement the learning instruction given to learners. Teachers. The teachers should have extended extra effort by conducting the oral lan-

guage development program to follow up on the lessons given to learners in the modules. Learners can be guided if the teachers give instructions on what to do in the activities that are found in the module. Future Researchers. The results and findings of this study will give insights to future researchers on the importance of oral language development as an advantage on the part of the learners. Oral Language Development Program. refers to the strategy initiated by the researcher to supplement instruction in the modules given to the learners. According to Wikipedia (2021) oral language development is an incredible opportunity to use your classroom skills in a new, profitable way.

Academic Performance. refers to the grades of the grade six learners who are beneficiaries of teaching. According to Wikipedia (2021), academic performance is the extent to which a student has attained his educational goals and is measured by assessment.

2. Method

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study makes use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent is a good design

when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 2020). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact groups of learners. This design is represented as follows:

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study will be conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Division of Digos City. The subjects of this study will be the 60 grade six learners – 32 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 28 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of

these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. The experiment will be conducted based on the mechanics of the Oral Language Development Program.

Number of Pupils in Each Section

Subjects	Section	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	32
2	Section B	28
Total		60

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teachers give modules at the same time meet the learners in face to face and adhere to the protocols of the Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners with the permission of parents during sessions to follow up on what has been printed in the module. The pre - and post-performance tests consist of 25-items that will

eventually determine the academic performance of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects to prior treatment. It assessed the effect of the oral language development program on the reading fluency of grade VI- pupils. The posttests administration measured the effect of the treatment determined on the oral language development program on the reading fluency of grade VI- pupils, the following continuum was based on the DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data gathering procedures, the researcher will draft a letter asking permission to conduct the research study to Melanie P. Estacio, CESOVI, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Digos City Davao Del Sur, and to the school principal. The letters were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent, and the school principal of Dawis Elementary School, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and validated by the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Dawis Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has

been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer the pretest to both controlled and experimental classes and eventually commence her experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer the posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make an analysis and interpretation of the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean

Performance Levels and Criteria

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, understanding and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge, skills, and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

will be used to describe the reading fluency of grade VI - pupils of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pretest and posttest. t-test for uncorrelated samples will be used to test the significance difference between

the pretest and posttest mean scores in the experimental and controlled groups. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude effect of the oral language development program on the reading fluency of grade VI- pupils.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence. Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationships of pre-tests, and post-tests scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade six pupils. The controlled group got the mean of 14.31 or Be-

ginning while the experimental group got the mean of 15.11 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	32	14.31	57.24	Beginning
Experimental Group	28	15.11	60.44	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during the pre-test the experimental group had a higher mean compared to the controlled group although both were Beginning levels. This finding was congruent to Dickinson Tabors (2021) who said that Oral language development plays a crucial role in a child’s overall literacy development, cognitive growth, and academic success. Oral language skills served as the foundation for literacy acquisition, providing the basis for reading, writing, and comprehension.

Implementing an oral language development program has various benefits for pupils, especially in terms of general language com-

petency and academic accomplishment. Oral language development programs can be particularly beneficial for culturally and linguistically diverse students, as they provide opportunities for students to develop proficiency in the language of instruction while maintaining and valuing their home languages and cultural identities (Garcia Wei, 2020). Post-Test Score of Pupils Table 2 disclosed the post-test scores of the grade six pupils. The controlled group got the mean of 20.52 or Developing while the experimental group got the mean of 21.63 or Approaching Proficiency.

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	32	20.52	82.08	Developing
Experimental Group	28	21.63	86.52	Approaching Proficiency

It can be gleaned from the table that during the post-test the experimental group had a higher mean compared to the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.52 from a mean rating of 15.11 to 21.63. This means that experimental group had a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding was congruent to Jenkins et.al (2021) idea who cited that the sixth graders’ reading fluency was found to be considerably enhanced by explicit training that focused on word recognition, fluency, and comprehension skills. To improve fluency abilities, they also stressed the significance of offering opportunities for repeated readings and feedback on how teaching methods affected sixth-grade students’ reading fluency. Oral language development programs implemented in

the early years of schooling can help identify and address potential learning difficulties, preventing academic challenges later on (Lonigan Shanahan, 2021). Oral language development programs support the development of speaking and listening skills, which are essential components of the Common Core State Standards for English Language Arts (National Governors Association Center for Best Practices Council of Chief State School Officers, 2019). By implementing oral language development programs, educators can effectively support students’ linguistic and academic growth, leading to improved outcomes across various domains. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post- Test Score.

Table 3 shows the test on the significant dif-

ference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.49 with a p-value of .0441 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade six

pupils. This implies that the used of oral language development program in teaching grade six have contributed the effectiveness in enhancing the reading fluency which is revealed by the scores of the six pupils.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	37	-5.49	.0441	Significant

This finding was in line with the statement of Hoff (2020) who said that oral language development was closely intertwined with literacy development. Strong oral language skills provide a foundation for reading and writing abilities. Children who have a rich oral language background often find it easier to comprehend written text and express themselves in writing. It's important to recognize and celebrate the diversity of languages and cultures in oral language development. Children from diverse linguistic backgrounds bring unique perspectives and experiences to their language learning journey. Supporting multilingualism and honoring different language practices contribute to inclusive and equitable language development. Early intervention through oral language development programs can help prevent academic achievement gaps, particularly for students from disadvantaged backgrounds. By providing targeted support to develop oral language skills, educators can mitigate disparities in academic outcomes (Hart Risley, 2020). Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and

Post test Scores of the Grade VI Pupils Table 4 highlights the test of oral language development programs on the reading fluency of grade six pupils. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.421 which signifies larger effects. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in developing reading fluency especially that reading is a critical component of literacy development, serving as a gateway to comprehension, academic success, and lifelong learning. For grade six pupils, who are transitioning to more advanced texts and subject matter, strong reading fluency is indispensable for navigating complex content with ease and confidence. Oral language development programs play a crucial role in fostering reading fluency and laying the groundwork for literacy success. By building phonemic awareness, expanding vocabulary, promoting language fluency and expression, cultivating comprehension skills, and enhancing reading motivation and engagement, these programs equip students with the foundational skills they need to become proficient readers and lifelong learners (Hoff, 2020).

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade VI Pupils

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
60	-4.38	0.421	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of oral language development programs on the reading fluency of grade six pupils. This study made use of quasi experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 2020). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Division of Digos City. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade six pupils – 32 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 28 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of oral language development program has increased the reading fluency of grade six pupils. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade six pupils both the controlled and experimental groups was at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group was at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group was at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade six students should use the oral language development program as a strategy that would further develop reading fluency of the students to make the teaching meaningful. Implementation of teaching strategies tailored to the needs of diverse learners, educators can create a dynamic and supportive learning environment

where students can develop the skills and strategies they need to become proficient readers. The school heads should promote the use of the oral language development program as a strategy that would enhance reading fluency as it is revealed in the study that it was effective on the subjects that were considered as a gateway to knowledge, comprehension, and critical thinking across all academic disciplines. A school policy about the utilization of oral language development programs can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session oral language development programs as a strategy in teaching.

For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of the oral language development program as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

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